

ISic3620

I.Sicily inscription 3620

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, catacomb of St. Paul and St. Agata, hypogeum no.14

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178088

1. ἐνθάδε [— — —]

2. Ω [— — — — —]

3. [.]NH [— —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645693

PHI 178088

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 59.1081

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni giudaica e cristiane di Malta. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 168: 202-208. At 202-203 no.1 ph

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.164

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3620. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388843>